

A PSEUDO-ENERGY BASED METHOD TO PREDICT FIBRE-MATRIX ADHESION USING A SINGLE FILAMENT COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The fragmentation test is now commonly used for measuring the fibre-matrix adhesion in a single filament polymer composite. The limitations of the current data reduction techniques used to calculate the value of interfacial shear strength from the fragmentation data are identified. Recently, we have proposed the plasticity effect model to accurately predict the stress profile in a single discontinuous fibre composite. This model can also be used to predict the stress fields in a single short fibre composite where debonding occurs at the fibre-matrix interface. In this paper, the plasticity effect model is used to develop a new pseudo-energy based data reduction technique for the fragmentation test. In this method, the interfacial shear stress associated with and the tensile stress in the individual fragments are predicted from the plasticity effect model and the total tensile stress transferred to all of the fibre fragments at a particular matrix strain is calculated. The total tensile stress transferred to all of the fibre fragments normalised against the fibre length is defined as the Cumulative Stress Transfer Function (CSTF). A glass fibre/epoxy system with different coupling agents is used for the validation of this technique.

INTRODUCTION

The fragmentation test is now commonly used to measure the interfacial shear strength of different fibre-matrix systems. When an external stress is applied to a single fibre embedded in the matrix, tensile stress is transferred to the fibre through an interfacial shear stress. As the tensile load increases, the tensile strain in the fibre will eventually exceed the failure strain of the fibre, and the fibre will fracture. The fibre continues to fracture into shorter lengths as the load increases, until the fragment length becomes too short to break.

The interfacial shear strength is calculated from the fragmentation test by assuming that the interfacial shear stress is constant over the fragment length either due to matrix flow in a completely plastic matrix or due to frictional stress transfer as a result of interfacial debonding. Based on the constant shear model proposed by Kelly and Tyson [1], the interfacial shear strength τ is given as

$$\tau = \frac{r_f \sigma_{fu}}{l_c}$$

Where r_f is the average fibre radius and σ_{fu} the tensile strength of the fibre at a length equal to the critical fibre length l_c . The critical fibre length from the average fibre fragment length is calculated using the relation given by Ohsawa et al [2] or Drzal et al [3,4].

Over the years, the following limitations of the constant shear model have emerged:

1. Laser Raman spectroscopy [5,6,7,8] and finite element analysis [9,10] have shown that the stress field assumption of the constant shear model is over-simplified.
2. Several studies have shown that the value of the interfacial shear strength obtained from the fragmentation test depends on the properties of the embedding resin even though the interface chemistry remains same [11,12]. Hence, the value of the interfacial shear strength obtained from the fragmentation test is not absolute.
3. The value of interfacial shear strength obtained from the fragmentation test in certain cases do not correlate with the expected surface chemistry e.g. the interfacial shear strength of water-sized, A1100 coupled glass fibres embedded in an epoxy resin is lower than that of water-sized, uncoupled glass fibre embedded in the same resin [13,14].
4. Contrary to the indications from laser Raman spectroscopy and finite element analysis [5,6,9,10], the value of the interfacial shear strength obtained from the fragmentation test in certain cases is higher than the shear yield strength of the matrix [10,14,15].
5. Highly ductile or elastomeric matrices can lead to very short fragment lengths during the fragmentation test due to better stress transfer efficiency of these resins. The use of the constant shear model in this case can lead to erroneously high values of interfacial shear strength [16].
6. The application of the constant shear model requires the saturation of the fibre fragmentation process during the fragmentation test. Hence, a very ductile matrix is used. This type of the matrix is seldom used in real-life composites.

Owing to the limitations of the constant shear model, several researchers incorporated the partial debonding model into the data reduction methodology for the fragmentation test. The partial debonding model of Piggott [18,19] combines the approach of the shear lag model of Cox [20] and frictional theory of Outwater [21]. Piggott's approach [19] was used by Lacroix et al [22] to develop a simulation to calculate interfacial shear strength from the fragmentation test. Later, the debonding stress obtained from the fibre pull-out test was incorporated into the above simulation to study the fibre fragmentation process [17,23]. However, the partial debonding model has the following limitations:

1. The partial debonding model considers either the shear yielding of the matrix or interfacial debonding at the end of the fibre fragment. Contrary to this, several studies have shown that interfacial debonding and shear yielding of the matrix can co-exist [5,6].
2. This model considers the stress transfer in the bonded region according to the shear lag model of Cox [20]. Recently, several micromechanical models have argued that the equilibrium boundary conditions in the shear lag model are not accurate [15,24].
3. In some cases, the value of the interfacial shear strength obtained using the partial debonding model can exceed the shear yield strength of the matrix [17,23], contrary to the indications from the finite element analysis and laser Raman spectroscopy [5,6,9,10].
4. The use of the partial debonding model requires a time consuming simulation process [17,22,23].
5. An accurate prediction of the interfacial shear strength from the fragmentation test requires the use of a predominantly elastic matrix. This may interfere with the fragment length saturation requirement of the fragmentation test [23].

The purpose of this paper is to propose a new data reduction method for the measurement of the fibre-matrix adhesion by the fragmentation test.

THE PLASTICITY EFFECT MODEL

Based on the finite element analysis of the stress fields in an isolated short fibre composite [9,10,16], Tripathi et al [25] proposed the plasticity effect model for the calculation of accurate stress profiles around short embedded fibre in a matrix. The plasticity effect model superimposes the elastic-plastic properties of the matrix on the variational model of Nairn in such a way that the resultant stress field accurately describes the stress transfer behaviour in a short embedded fibre composite. Furthermore, Coulomb's law is used to calculate the stress transfer in the debonded fibre region. The detailed model is presented elsewhere [25]. The tensile stress at the centre of the fibre and shear stress at the fibre-matrix interface predicted from the plasticity effect model, the shear lag model of Cox, the variational model of Nairn and the elastic-plastic finite element model are compared in Figs 1 and 2. It can be seen that the stress field predictions from the plasticity effect model compare very well with those from the elastic-plastic finite element model. Furthermore, the plasticity effect model predicts that the interfacial shear stress is zero at the end of the fibre and that the matrix near the fibre end always yields irrespective of the presence or absence of interfacial debonding or transverse matrix cracking in the fragmentation test specimen. Thus, the plasticity effect model questions the existence of "a characteristic interfacial shear strength" obtained from the fragmentation test. In the absence of a characteristic interfacial shear strength, the tensile stress transferred to the embedded fibre across the interface is taken as a measure of the quality of the interface.

Fig. 1. Shear stress at the fibre-matrix interface of a short embedded fibre predicted by the plasticity effect model and other micromechanical models in comparison with that from finite element analysis

THE CSTF METHOD

The calculation of fibre-matrix adhesion from the proposed method is based on the assumption that the number and length of individual fibre fragments in a fragmentation test specimen depend on the quality of the interface and that a good interface transfers more tensile stress to the embedded reinforcing fibre in comparison to a poor interface. In this method, the interfacial shear stress associated with a fibre fragment is calculated from the plasticity effect model. From this shear stress profile, tensile stress profile in the fibre fragment is calculated using the "balance

of the force argument" [25]. The tensile stress profile in the fibre fragment is integrated over the fragment length to calculate the stress transfer function (STF). The value of the tensile stress transferred (STF) is summed across all the fibre fragments and normalised to the total length of the fragments. This normalised value is called cumulative stress transfer function or CSTF.

Fig. 2. Tensile stress at the centre of an embedded fibre predicted by the plasticity effect model and other micromechanical models in comparison with that from finite element analysis

It is expected that the final distribution of the fibre fragment lengths will depend on the flaw size and distribution in the embedded fibre. However, the final fragment distribution will be an exclusive function of the fibre surface treatment, providing the fibre strength remains constant after the surface treatment. The effect of the fibre strength statistics on the proposed data reduction technique will be discussed later. The fibre and matrix properties, and the sample dimensions used for the calculations are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Sample dimensions and material properties used for the calculation of CSTF value

Fibre radius (μm)	7.35
Elastic modulus of the fibre (GPa)	76
Poisson's ratio of the fibre	0.25
Shear yield strength of the matrix (MPa)	24.79
Shear cold draw strength of the matrix (MPa)	18.85
Elastic modulus of the matrix (GPa)	2.46
Friction coefficient (μ)	0.5
Applied stress (MPa)	246
Fibre volume fraction (V_f)	0.004

EXPERIMENTAL AND RESULTS

The water-sized, uncoupled glass fibre was supplied by Owens-Corning Fiberglas. The fibre properties are presented elsewhere [10]. The fibre was treated with A1100 coupling agent and the procedure is presented elsewhere [13,14,26]. The epoxy resin used for the fragmentation test

was a combination of Epikote 828 (Shell) and Araldite CY208 (Ciba-Geigy). Epikote 828 is a diglycidyl ether of Bisphenol-A and Araldite CY208 is a blend of long chain aliphatic epoxy resin and Bisphenol-A. A combination of the curing agents, Nadic methylene anhydride (Stag Polymers and Sealants) and Capcure 3-800 (Henkel Performance Chemicals) was used for curing of epoxy resin. The details of the epoxy resin formulation, curing schedule and mechanical properties are presented elsewhere [10,26]. The details of the fragmentation test procedure and data reduction technique are also presented elsewhere [10,13,14]. The fragmentation test results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. The fibre-matrix adhesion predicted by the fragmentation test using the different data reduction techniques (Standard deviation in brackets).

Fibre treatment	ISS from the conventional data reduction technique (MPa) [26]	CSTF value based on Plasticity effect model (MPa m/m)
Water-sized uncoupled	49.08 (11.96)	479
Water-sized A1100 coupled	40.58 (7.71)	543

DISCUSSIONS

VALIDATION OF THE METHODOLOGY

It is necessary to perform some primary analysis of the data reduction technique to confirm its validity. A series of the fibre fragments shown in Table 3 was chosen to examine the effect of applied stress on the STF value. Fragments A and C are the smallest and the longest fibre fragments respectively, observed at the end of a particular fragmentation test. Fragment B is the average of fibre fragments A and C. It is obvious from the STF values of fragments A to C that the STF value increases with the fragment length. This is not surprising since the plasticity effect model and the CSTF methodology assume that a longer fibre experiences more shear yielding of the matrix in comparison to a smaller fibre fragment. Thus, effectively the stress transferred to a longer fibre fragment is higher as reflected by the higher STF value. However, the STF value reduces if the interfacial debonding occurs at the fibre end (Fragments B & D). Furthermore, a longer fibre may have a lower STF value in comparison to a shorter fibre depending on the extent of the interfacial debonding (Fragments D & E). Hence, STF value of a fibre fragment is the function of fibre length and the extent of interfacial debonding.

Table 3. STF value of different arbitrary fibre fragments to show the validity of the CSTF method

Fragment name	Type of the fragment	Fragment length (μm)	Debonding length (μm)	STF value (MPa m/m)
A	Short without debonding	165	0	190.26
B	Medium without debonding	497.5	0	588.78
C	Long without debonding	830	0	890.58
D	Medium with short debonding length	497.5	50	552.72
E	Medium with long debonding length	550	150	467.69

The fibre fragmentation process results in a series of fibre fragments of unequal lengths. As discussed above, the STF value of a fibre fragment increases with the fibre length provided the

extent of the interfacial debonding remains same. But it does not imply that a fragmentation test specimen with higher average fragment length will have higher CSTF value in comparison to the another with lower average fibre length. Or, in other words, two fibre fragmentation test specimens with the same average fragment length may have different CSTF values. For example, the combined STF value of fragments A and C is not double of the STF value of the fragment B. Hence, the CSTF value of a fragmentation test specimen is an exclusive function of the distribution of the fibre fragment lengths.

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The interfacial shear strength calculated using the constant shear model and CSTF value calculated on the basis of plasticity effect model for water-sized, uncoupled glass fibre and water-sized, A1100 coupled glass fibre embedded in the epoxy resin are shown in Table 2. It can be seen that the interfacial shear strength obtained using the constant shear model is higher than the shear yield strength of the matrix (Table 1). The shear yield strength of the matrix based on von Mises stress criterion is 24.79 MPa. It can be seen that the value of interfacial shear strength for A1100 coupled glass fibre is less than that for uncoupled glass fibre. These results are in line with the values of interfacial shear strength reported by Cheng et al [14] for glass fibre/vinyl ester resin system. The authors [14] explained the lower interfacial shear strength in the case of the silanised glass fibre by the formation of a polymeric layer of A1100 rather than a monolayer. However, when the authors [14] treated A1100 coupled glass fibre with the hot water to promote the formation of a monolayer of silane coupling agent on the glass fibre surface before embedding it in the resin, the value of the interfacial shear strength exceeded the value of interfacial shear strength of water-sized uncoupled glass fibre. However, the same effect of the silanes could not be repeated for the glass fibres embedded in an epoxy matrix. The calculation of the fibre-matrix adhesion based on CSTF method has shown that the CSTF value of water-sized, A1100 coupled glass fibre is higher than that of the water-sized, uncoupled glass fibre.

THE EFFECT OF WEIBULL MODULUS

As discussed earlier, the Weibull modulus of the embedded fibre plays a very important role in the fragment length distribution during the fragmentation test. Consequently, the fragment length distribution at the end of the fragmentation test is a function of the interface quality as well as fibre strength statistics. The strength characteristics of the fibre fragment change when different surface treatments are applied to the fibre at the laboratory scale [14]. However, it has been observed that the deterioration of the fibre strength is insignificant during the fibre surface treatment carried out under the carefully controlled conditions [26]. It is necessary for the fibre strength to be preserved during the surface treatment in the laboratory in order to segregate the effect of Weibull modulus from the quality of the interface. However, this complication is advantageous when the same surface treatment is applied in the manufacturing plant. For example, a particular sizing resin application can lead to either a reduction or an improvement in the fibre strength as a result of poor or improved handleability of the fibre rovings. Because of the complications of the manufacturing process, the fibre strength characteristics cannot be maintained. Similarly, a particular surface treatment applied to the carbon fibre may modify the interface chemistry as well as the fibre strength. In certain cases, the improvement in the interface adhesion may be offset by the reduction of the fibre strength, thereby, leading to no improvement or even reduction in the overall mechanical properties of the composite. Hence, it is necessary that the combined effect of the fibre-matrix interface and fibre strength due to a particular surface treatment is considered for evaluation of the interfacial properties to achieve an overall improvement in the mechanical properties of the fibre reinforced composites. The conventional data reduction techniques for the fragmentation test are not suitable to study the combined effect of the fibre strength and interfacial adhesion.

ADVANTAGES OF THE CSTF TECHNIQUE

The CSTF technique for measuring the fibre-matrix adhesion from the fragmentation test has the following advantages over the other data reduction techniques.

1. It takes the specimen geometry and applied strain into consideration.
2. It calculates the stress profile around the individual fibre fragments based on an accurate plasticity effect method and all the relevant tensile, shear and radial stresses and elasto-plastic properties of the matrix are taken into account.
3. The stress transfer due to the interfacial debonding is also considered.
4. The calculation of a cumulative stress transfer function does not require a time-consuming simulation process.
5. Since the value of the CSTF can be calculated at any applied strain, it is not sensitive to the saturation of the fibre fragmentation process. This implies that a matrix similar to that used in real-life composite can be used for the fragmentation test provided a sufficient number of the fibre fragments is obtained.
6. Since CSTF value is a direct measure of the efficiency of the stress transfer to the fibre across the interface, the correlation of the fragmentation test (a micromechanical test) with the macromechanic tests will be easier.
7. The results, so far, indicate that the adhesion measured by the micromechanical test agrees well with the surface chemistry.

LIMITATIONS OF THE CSTF TECHNIQUE

1. The use of CSTF technique is based on the assumption that the stress profile around an embedded fragment can be successfully predicted using the plasticity effect model. This implies that the predictions by CSTF technique are subject of the quality of the predictions by the plasticity effect model. Furthermore, the assumptions and limitations of the plasticity effect model are also valid here [25].
2. A careful selection of the mechanical properties of the embedding resin is necessary to minimise the errors in the calculation of CSTF value.
3. The CSTF value obtained from the fragmentation test is a function of the applied strain and, hence, the CSTF values of the fibres with different surface treatments at a similar applied strain should be compared.
4. The validity and applicability of CSTF method for other fibre surface treatments is the subject of ongoing research.

CONCLUSIONS

The various data reduction techniques used for calculating the value of the interfacial shear strength from the fragmentation test are reviewed. It has been concluded that the data reduction methodologies based on the constant shear model or the partial debonding model have several severe limitations. Because of the strong influence of the matrix plasticity on the stress transfer in a single fibre composite observed by the finite element analysis and laser Raman spectroscopy, the conventional definition of the interfacial shear strength is questioned. A new data reduction technique, known as CSTF technique, is developed to measure fibre-matrix adhesion from the fragmentation test. In this technique, the total stress transferred to an embedded fibre is calculated on the basis of the plasticity effect model. This technique has been used to measure the fibre-matrix adhesion of glass fibre-epoxy resin system.

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